

Original Article

Analyzing Effects of Rich Instruction on Word Knowledge of Young ESL Learners

Amna Zuhra¹, Ubaidullah Abid Qazi², Sidra Ahmad³

¹MS Scholar, Foundation University School of Science and Technology, Foundation University Islamabad.

²Assistant Professor, Foundation University School of Science and Technology, Foundation University Islamabad.

³Lecturer, Foundation University School of Science and Technology, Foundation University Islamabad.

Abstract

Developing Deep Word Knowledge and active vocabulary is the biggest challenge faced by ESL learners in Pakistan. Hence, there is a need to assess the merits of Rich Instruction that aims in developing Word Knowledge and active vocabulary of ESL learners. The current study aimed to investigate the effect of Rich Instruction in developing Word Knowledge in young ESL learners. The study examined whether or not Rich Instruction is being used to develop Word Knowledge at the primary level in Pakistani ESL classrooms. It further investigated up to what extent and which aspects of the Word Knowledge (viz. form, meaning, and use) are most effectively developed by various activities involved in Rich Instruction. The survey was conducted to confirm if Rich Instruction is being used to develop Word Knowledge at the primary level in Pakistani ESL classrooms using semi-structured interviews as a tool. The sample of 15 English teachers was selected by purposive sampling from 15 English medium schools. The pre-experimental one-group pre and posttest design was used to analyze the effect of Rich Instruction on the various aspects of Word Knowledge. For this purpose, young ESL learners of grade 4 were selected as a subject of the experiment. The findings of survey revealed that Rich Instruction is not practiced as a dedicated way of teaching and developing Word Knowledge in Pakistani ESL classrooms at the primary level. The findings of the experimental study revealed that activities involved in Rich Instruction showed a significant effect on the various aspects of Word Knowledge. Use and Form exhibited good improvement when students were taught with activities involved in Rich Instruction, whereas Meaning represented less improvement. It was concluded that Rich Instruction and activities can be used as an effective instructional technique in the classroom to develop Word Knowledge and active vocabulary of young ESL learners.

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INTRODUCTION

English language functions as a significant academic and communicative tool around the world. In Pakistan, the rise of the middle class and subsequent increase in access to formal education has escalated the demand for efficient teaching of this global lingua franca to the students who learn English as their second language. The past few years have brought a significant increase in the interactive pedagogies for English as

* Corresponding Author: Sidra Ahmad | Lecturer, Foundation University School of Science and Technology, Foundation University Islamabad.

✉ sidra.ahmad@fui.edu.pk

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Second Language (ESL) learners. However, despite giving so much importance to English language and teaching techniques, the standards of English language do not seem to have improved as much. The young ESL learners in Pakistan face huge problems in their schools and continue to struggle throughout their studies. They lag behind in language competencies, especially in English that is rooted in weak vocabulary growth which makes them unable to comprehend others and express their ideas effectively. This highlights the significance of vocabulary development in ESL learners' and draws attention towards effective teaching techniques for the development of Word Knowledge.

Unfortunately, the building of active vocabulary and deep WK remains largely neglected by the English language teachers in ESL classrooms, and it hinders their expressive speech in English language. The significant role of vocabulary development has gained the attention of many linguists who have been keen in exploring various ways to develop deep WK and active vocabulary of ESL learners. Although there are many researches have been made in the field of vocabulary education but few researches have highlighted effective vocabulary instructions and their importance in developing deep Word Knowledge of English language. Therefore, it is very important to find the most effective way of vocabulary instruction to develop deep word knowledge in English Language Teaching (ELT).

Developing Deep Word Knowledge and active vocabulary of ESL learners in Pakistan is hampered by various factors. Part of the reason lies in the way they are taught vocabulary by using different instructions in ESL classrooms. Traditional instructions include explicit (flashcards, wordlists, read aloud, dictionaries, memorization drills), and implicit (reading and writing activities) way of teaching vocabulary that primarily focuses on the spoken or written Form of the word and its connection to the Meaning of the words while neglecting the Use (collocations, registers, etc.) aspect of the word. Therefore, there is a need to see whether building the deep WK of ESL learners leads to greater active vocabulary usage and more effective communication. For this purpose, the use of Rich Instruction in the ESL classrooms is the main stream in having the significant effect in developing the WK, and will aid in enhancing active vocabulary of ESL learners. So, keeping in view the above mentioned facts, the existing research is planned to analyze the efficacy of Rich Instruction (RI) in developing Word Knowledge of young ESL learners.

Nation's (2001) View on Word Knowledge

The knowledge of word (WK) includes multiple aspects, ranging from simple pronunciation and orthographic presentation of the word to the syntactic and pragmatic use of the word. Nation (2001) provides three significant aspects of a word that include what it really means to know a word. (a) The *form* of a word includes its pronunciation (spoken form), spelling (written form), and word parts (i.e. prefix, root, and suffix). (b) The *meaning* involves the way that form and meaning work in combination (form and meaning), the concept and what items it refers to (concept and referents), and the associations of the word. (c) The *use* encompasses the grammatical functions of a word, when and where to use a word (constraints on its use) and collocations of the word. Deep Word Knowledge does not just lie in knowing one aspect of word or making form and meaning connections rather it involves getting knowledge of as many as different aspects of WK that is equally important (Schmitt, 2007).

Rich Instruction as a Productive Approach to Vocabulary Teaching

Rich instruction is a productive approach to vocabulary teaching that is first developed by Beck and her coworkers in the 1980's that aims to focus on the deep knowledge of words' meaning by creating semantic links to words, and to promote greater facility in using words. It is based on the idea that understanding of a text requires more knowledge than just knowing the basic definitions of the word. RI instruction seeks to develop active vocabulary and deep knowledge of the word by using activities that focuses on all aspects of the words: interacting with words in diverse contexts by providing multiple exposures to the word to strengthen relationships among the word. Rich Instruction became an instructional approach to teach vocabulary to learners. According to Nation (2001) Rich instruction includes giving elaborate attention to a word by going beyond the immediate or specific context of occurrence. There are multiple ways of providing RI in language classrooms. One of the ways is to employ RI activities in the language classrooms. In RI, the instructor spends time on the word by integrating various activities in the language classroom to teach all aspects of the same word (Nation and Hunston, 2013). These activities assist learners to develop deep WK and make accurate use of the knowledge of target words in their expressive speech.

Rich Instruction Activities

Rich Instruction activities are the backbone of Rich Instruction. Nation and Hunston (2013) give a range of activities for Rich Instruction that would include giving due consideration to various aspects for the same word. They have categorized RI activities according to several aspects of WK. These activities can be effective in deepening the WK of young ESL learners. These activities focus on the Form (spoken form, written form, and word parts), Meaning (form-meaning connection, concept and reference and associations), and Use (grammatical functions, constraints on use, and collocations) of the word.

Need for Effective Vocabulary Instruction in Young Learners

Findings from different studies have revealed that children start to learn and develop knowledge of words in primary grades. Various scholars have agreed on the view that vocabulary learning must begin in primary schools. Dickinson and Tabors (2001) highlighted in their study that vocabulary knowledge gained at early age is linked to the comprehension in higher schools. Similarly, Biemiller (2005) agrees that vocabulary gaps could be filled and comprehension could be improved during young age by using focused vocabulary instructions. Beck, McKeown, and Kucan (2002) further strengthens this view that there is a considerable gap in the word knowledge of the young learners, and the gap widens as learners advances in higher grades. This gap ultimately leads to poor language skills, including fluency and accuracy. This highlights that vocabulary instruction is an important factor in primary schools.

Moreover, there are some kinds of words that are not likely to develop naturally in young learners and require focused instruction to understand different texts, known as Tier 2 words or the more sophisticated forms of words. For example, ‘enormous’ is the sophisticated form of the word ‘big’ or ‘absurd’ is the refined version of ‘silly’. Researchers suggest that tier 2 words have a significant part in a language users’ list of words, and rich knowledge of words can have a powerful effect on the expressive language of learners. Also, teachers should employ Rich Instruction on Tier 2 words, as developing deep WK and active vocabulary is most certainly a goal of RI. Studies suggest the use of substantial Rich Instruction in the primary grades language classrooms.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this research is to confirm if Rich Instruction is being used to develop Word Knowledge in Pakistani ESL classrooms at primary level. This study also aims to analyze the impact of Rich Instruction in developing the Word Knowledge of young ESL learners and assesses various aspects of Word Knowledge which are affected by the use of activities involved in Rich Instruction.

Research Questions

1. Whether or not Rich Instruction is being used to develop Word Knowledge in Pakistani ESL classrooms at the primary level?
2. What is the impact of Rich Instruction in developing the Word Knowledge of young ESL learners?
3. How do the activities involved in Rich Instruction affect the various aspects of Word Knowledge of young ESL learners?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Many research workers made significant contribution in the field of effective vocabulary instruction and developing WK. Beck and McKeown (2001) conducted a study on the vocabularies of grade one students, at primary level to see the improvement in the vocabularies using read-aloud activity involved in Rich Instruction. The findings of the study showed that employing Rich Instruction had an effective for increasing primary grade students’ Word Knowledge of Tier 2 words by using read-aloud activity. Similarly, Beck et al. (2002) carried out their study on the significance of vocabulary instruction (RI) in the development of reading comprehension. Their findings showed that vocabulary instruction had a significant effect on the word knowledge of children when they were taught Tier 2 academic words is effective to develop their vocabulary knowledge. These both studies conclude RI approach helps to build the Word Knowledge of tier 2 words. Likewise, McKeown and Beck (2004) also points out basic aims of Rich Instruction: it actively involves learners in thinking about the word and its meanings, enables them how the words are used in different contexts, and relationship among the words. RI is a well-balanced vocabulary program that has proven to be an effective way of instruction that focuses on the active use of vocabulary of a learner and helps in strengthening the WK of young ESL learners.

The research scholars have conducted various studies to determine the effects of employing rich vocabulary instructions and its importance in developing different language skills of ESL learners. Findings from studies of Beck and McKeown (2007) suggest that RI is effective for even early graders from low-socioeconomic backgrounds, and they can effectively learn and use refined versions of vocabulary in a language. The findings showed that children exposed to instruction in the experimental group learned significantly more words. Similarly, Yonek (2008) investigated the effects of Rich Vocabulary Instruction (RVOI) on students' expository writing. The participants were fourth grade students who were taught twelve tier 2 words for five days. She found that students who received RVOI outperformed than the students who received traditional instruction. The findings showed that rich instruction is more effective for students in learning and deepening of Word Knowledge that ultimately assist them to utilize newly learned words in the formation of complex texts such as writing.

Brydon (2010) highlighted the effectiveness of Rich Instruction on the vocabulary acquisition of 3 to 5 year old preschool bilingual learners in Pennsylvania. The participants were 21 students who were taught vocabulary by engaging in RI activities. The findings showed that the way in which children were taught by exposing learners to Rich Instruction activities showed effective results in developing the knowledge of Tier 2 words in children. The study exhibited the importance of activities used in the Rich Instruction not only improved their Word Knowledge but also helped learners to utilize their WK in expressive speech, hence proving to be a practical vocabulary instruction in language classrooms. Nilfroushan (2012) studied the effect of teaching vocabulary through semantic mapping in developing deep and general vocabulary knowledge. An experimental study was conducted on sixty intermediate (treatment $n = 30$; control $n = 30$) EFL learners using vocabulary achievement pretest and posttest. The result showed that the use of semantic mapping affected the deep and general vocabulary knowledge of students with a higher difference in the mean score of both posttest and pretest. This implies that word map activity aids in building students' productive and receptive Word Knowledge.

Vadasy, Sanders and Becky (2014) investigated the effect of Rich Instruction on the comprehension and Word Knowledge of young students studying in four and five class in urban elementary school. An experimental study was designed by using 1276 subjects for experimentation. The experimental group showed improvement in the reading comprehension and vocabulary of learners. They added RI develops the knowledge of words on a productive level rather than simply on a receptive level. Reza and Ashouri (2016) carried out a study to explore the impact of lexical collocation activity on the vocabulary size of intermediate EFL learners in Iran. Experimental study was designed using 84 subjects for experimentation. The findings showed outstanding results as the students' vocabulary knowledge enhanced remarkably after the adoption of collocation instruction. The experimental group showed improvement in their vocabulary sphere by the help of learning collocation group. The study recommends that collocation teaching can be used as an alternative for increasing the vocabulary knowledge of L2 language.

McKeown, Crosson, Moore and Beck (2018) exhibited a study to examine the effect of vocabulary intervention in expanding Word Knowledge and comprehension of language learners. An experimental study was designed using 105 (treatment $n = 62$; control $n = 43$) subjects for experimentation. The participants for the study were students of sixth grade. The findings showed that vocabulary intervention affected the word knowledge, lexical access, and morphological awareness of the participants in experimental group. The study revealed the importance of vocabulary intervention as it helped the learners to expand their word knowledge and understanding, hence proving to be central to language teaching.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In view of above mentioned work represented by different researchers, the present was designed to investigate the use of RI to develop Word Knowledge in Pakistani ESL classrooms at primary level using survey method having semi-structured interviews. The collected data for the survey study using SSIs was analyzed by using thematic analysis (TA) based on the model provided by Braun and Clarke (2006) for 'identifying, analyzing, organizing, describing, and writing themes or patterns in the data. The current study has used the Word Knowledge model provided by Paul Nation (Nation, 2001) combined with Rich Instruction offered by Nation and Hunston (2013) to analyze the effect of Rich Instruction in enriching the Word Knowledge of young ESL learners. The study used experimental method to determine whether there is any significant impact of RI activities on Word Knowledge of ESL learners and will also identify which

aspect of word Knowledge (form, meaning, and use) can be significantly improved by utilizing activities involved in Rich Instruction which are affected by the use of Rich Instruction activities. A pre-experimental design, having one group pretest-post-test design was used to compare two sets of data from the same groups that is proposed by Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2007).

Participants and Sampling

The participants selected for the survey study were English teachers from both private and public English medium schools of Pakistan. The total participants of the survey study were fifteen English teachers. The selection of English teacher was based on the experience to ESL teaching and having awareness of modern teaching techniques. The participants for the experimental study were the fourth-grade students who have been studying English language since the early years of their education. The total number selected participants in fourth-grade were eighteen. The (two stage) purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants from the population of both survey and experimental study.

Instruments for Data Collection

The instruments used to collect data for the survey method was Semi-Structured interviews. It consisted of set of five semi-structured interview questions related to the use of Rich Instruction as a vocabulary teaching technique in ESL classrooms. The research instrument used in the experimental method was English Word Knowledge (EWK) pretest and posttest. In order to measure three aspects of word knowledge, EWK test will be used as pretests and posttests. These tests consisted of three sections. The first section had a spelling test in which the participants had to write down the words that they will hear from English teacher. It is to assess the form aspect of the word. The next two sections will be based on the Word-associates Test (Read, 2000) with the aim of measuring two other aspects of Word Knowledge: meaning and use. To score the tests, the researcher will create a rubric by using the techniques provided by Read (2000) to assess various aspects of the Word Knowledge which include form, meaning, and use.

Materials and Scoring Rubric for Experimental Study

The researcher consulted British National Corpus (BNC) for the collocations to design the test. The researcher also took help from Merriam Webster thesaurus Oxford dictionary, Collins dictionary and vocabulary profiles to design EWK tests by taking into account the meanings, synonyms, grammatical functions, and formal and informal usage of the words used in the text. The English WK test of ESL learner was evaluated by creating a Rubric with the help of guidelines and techniques and to assess their performance in written pre and posttests. To assess various aspects of the WK including Form, Meaning and, Use, an English WK evaluation rubric was used. Scoring procedures to assess each aspect of WK are described in detail. To assess the Form aspect of the WK, the researcher created a Pronunciation and Dictation Evaluation Rubric using guidelines provided by Fountain and Nation (2001). Each correct answer was given one (1) point and zero (0) point was given to each incorrect answer.

Procedure

The experimental study was conducted in the city of Rahim Yar Khan, in a private educational institute after selection of fourth-grade students as participants. Then the skilled English primary school teacher was approached, who was aware of the purpose of the research to carry out a study in her supervision. After few sessions and discussions with the teacher, the plan of the study was prepared. It consisted of three stages. Firstly, the EWK of the students of experimental group was assessed by conducting a written EWK pretest. It consisted of questions related to the form, meaning, and use of the word. The reason for taking written pretest is to assess the students' active knowledge of words in terms of form, meaning and use. These aspects of WK were assessed by using a rubric created by the researcher. Secondly, these students were taught English vocabulary words by using Rich Instruction and activities. A list of target words were selected as depicted in the Table 1. The researcher helped the teacher to make lesson plans integrated with these activities. A set of activities were selected that fit into a 5-day weekly schedule. Students were given opportunities to develop their Word Knowledge deep enough to use it in their expressive speech. The time period of the treatment stage was seven weeks. At the end of the treatment, the students EWK was assessed again using posttest.

1	Week 1	Set A	Inhospitable, Consumed, Gluttonously, Desperate
2	Week 2	Set B	Leaped, Plunge, Slender, Amazement
3	Week 3	Set C	Anguish, Gobble, Astonishment, Grabbed
4	Week 4	Set D	Devastation, Enthusiasm, Approached, Exquisite
5	Week 5	Set E	Hesitantly, Admiring, Exceptional, Diminish
6	Week 6	Set F	Sternly, Relented, Scorched, Parched
7	Week 7	Set G	Impatiently, Glinting, Crumbled, Sorrowfully

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of the survey study showed that widely used techniques to teach English vocabulary include fill in the blanks, words meanings, vocabulary games, dictations, word sentences, matching columns, and choose the correct word in a phrase. Results also revealed that majority of the teachers only use same activities daily to enhance vocabulary and do not change activities on the daily basis when they were asked how often do they change activities to teach vocabulary of English to learners at primary level. Results found from SSIs also revealed that English teachers that are teaching at primary level in English medium schools do not use Rich Instruction as dedicated way of teaching English as a second language. Infact, majority of the teachers were not familiar that Rich Instruction is a latest trend in the teaching to enhance active vocabulary and WK for better expression and effective communication. The commonly used activities to teach vocabulary in Pakistani ESL classrooms at primary level include, read aloud, flash cards, fill in the blanks, words meanings, vocabulary games, dictations, word sentences, matching columns and choose the correct word in a phrase. The findings also lead to the conclusion that majority of the teachers are not familiar with the Rich Instruction technique and they prefer to teach vocabulary using conventional teaching methods.

The results of the experimental study showed that the pre-test mean score by using conventional teaching method was 51.0 and the posttest means core was 73.9; that is, the achievement in the WK of the fourth graders after being exposed to Rich Instruction which was higher than the pre-test mean scores is illustrated in Figure 1.

	WK Pretest (%)	WK Post Test (%)
Mean	51.05556	73.94444
Mean Difference	22.88	

After calculating the mean scores of pre and posttests, the scores were subsequently entered in Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Statistics 21 for the analyses, and the mean scores of WK pre and posttest were calculated through a paired t-test at 5% level to check the significant difference in the values of WK pretest and posttest. The data packed in the Table 2 were analyzed by utilizing mean, standard deviation, standard error mean, and t-test. Paired sample t-test for the significance of Word Knowledge is given in the Table 2. This table reflects that when combined pre to posttest gains are measured for all three WK aspects, the overall effect of Rich Instruction is statistically significant.

Word Knowledge Pre & Post Test		Paired Differences					T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% confidence interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	WK-pretest & WK-posttest	-22.88	3.5461	.83584	-24.6523	-21.1254	-27.384	17	.000

WK= Word Knowledge

In order to assess which aspect of WK can be significantly improved by using activities involved in RI, the mean values of pretest and posttest for all the three aspects of Word Knowledge viz., form, meaning, and use of young ESL learners were calculated through *descriptive statistics* using SPSS software. Then, the difference in the mean scores of all three aspects of the Word Knowledge was calculated to rank the level of improvement in each aspect of WK. The descriptive statistics including mean, standard deviation and ranking of each aspect of WK for the 18 participants are reported in Table 3. Difference in the means of different aspects of Word Knowledge is also depicted in Table 3 below.

Aspects of Word Knowledge pre & posttest		N	Mean	SEM	SD	Difference in pre & posttest means	Ranking
Pair 1	F-pretest	18	17.6667	.98020	4.15862	8.38	2
	F-posttest	18	26.0556	.56286	2.38801		
Pair 2	M-pretest	18	17.3889	.54316	2.30444	5.61	3
	M-posttest	18	23.0000	.65679	2.78652		
Pair 3	U-pretest	18	16.0000	.51131	2.16930	8.88	1
	U-posttest	18	24.8889	.71350	3.02711		

F= Form, M= meaning, U=use

Overall, the results in Table 3 suggest that there were significant differences in development of WK of young ESL learners from pre-test to posttest, but the level of development in scores of different aspects of WK was comparable from pretest to posttest in students and could be ranked favorably.

The results of the experimental study showed a significant improvement in Word Knowledge after conducting the experiment. The results revealed that the overall effect of Rich Instruction was statistically significant as it improved their WK. The results also showed differences in the means scores of various aspects of WK. The highest difference was recorded in the mean scores of use aspect of WK which was (M= 8.88). This revealed that the use of Word Knowledge improved in students remarkably up to a great extent. The students were able to make accurate use of the words in different contexts. The other aspect that also improved significantly was form showing significant difference of (M= 8.34) in pretest and posttest. The students showed improvement in their WK as they were able to make correct forms of the word. The aspect which showed significant difference at low ranking was Meaning aspect of the Word Knowledge having difference of (M= 5.61) in both the pretest and posttest.

The findings of the experimental study showed that when students were taught using Rich instruction activities such as read-aloud cutting up complex words, building complex words, choosing the correct form, using word cards, peer teaching, discussing the meaning of phrases, playing at word detectives, peer teaching, finding common meaning, finding substitutes (word associations), matching and finding collocations and identifying constraints their Word Knowledge was significantly improved. These findings of the current study put forward that the activities and RI that were incorporated in each English class assisted

students to enrich their Word Knowledge. In addition, the study found that the frequent exposure of the words in RI enhanced students understanding of the unfamiliar words that allowed the learners to practice vocabulary in the EFL classrooms and hence assists in enriching their deep Word Knowledge. These activities provided EFL learner's with multiple opportunities for engagement through elaboration, discussion and thinking about words. The above discussion establishes that the findings of the current study has provided evidence that Rich Instruction and the activities involved in RI are effective in improving and developing deep Word Knowledge of the learners.

CONCLUSION

The survey study revealed that Rich Instruction is not used as a dedicated way of teaching and developing Word Knowledge in Pakistani ESL classrooms at the primary level. The experimental study revealed that Rich Instruction has a significant impact on the Word Knowledge of ESL learners. Moreover, the results and findings of the study also revealed that all aspects of Word Knowledge were improved effectively when applied Rich Instruction activities in ESL classroom. The development and improvement in each aspect form, meaning, and use, was significant respectively.

The conclusions can be drawn from above mentioned findings that the use of Rich Instruction and activities involved in RI are effective to develop deep Word Knowledge and are significant in improving WK of young ESL learners. Focusing on the Word Knowledge and various aspects of WK of a learner helps in developing their Word Knowledge and enhances their active vocabulary. The findings of the study reflect that RI is effective in developing deep Word Knowledge of young ESL learners. It was also found that Rich Instruction is a well-balanced program and is superior to traditional teaching methods of vocabulary development, as it is significant in facilitating depth of Word Knowledge.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It is sought from the findings of the study that there is a need of effective vocabulary instructional program in schools to enhance students' Word Knowledge and active vocabularies. The people in the field of language and teaching should collaborate to encourage integration of Rich Instructional program in language classrooms. The teachers need to be aware of the implementation of Rich instructional program with an integration of Rich instruction activities in the classrooms can yield positive results in the field of education and develops active vocabulary in the learners. It is yearned that there is a need to make revisions in the English curriculum by adding RI activities in the English text books at the end of each chapter that enhances and focuses on the various aspects of WK.

Suggestions for the Future Study

A similar study could be replicated by taking a larger sample for survey study, and by adopting questionnaires to generalize results on larger populations. The future study could make an attempt to make a comparison between the impact of traditional vocabulary and RI teaching method to investigate which method is better to enhance students' active vocabulary and deep Word Knowledge enough to use it in their expressive speech. The studies related to inclusion of Rich Instructional program and effective vocabulary teaching techniques in syllabuses can be conducted to develop students' deep Word Knowledge and active vocabularies. This study investigates the impact of Rich instruction on the Word Knowledge of ESL learners. Further research is needed to find the impact of Rich instruction on students' speaking and listening skills.

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